

**ATTENTION TO RELIGIOUS VALUES IN THE
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18517100>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 05th February 2026Accepted: 06th February 2026Online: 07th February 2026**KEYWORDS**

religious values, freedom of conscience, New Uzbekistan, religious tolerance, spirituality, civil society, socio-philosophical analysis, enlightenment, immunity against extremism, interethnic harmony

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the essence of attention to religious values in the Republic of Uzbekistan, its socio-philosophical foundations, and its role in the life of the state and society. In the study, religious values are considered as an important factor in shaping the spiritual world of a person, stabilizing the moral environment in society, and raising civic consciousness. The article also scientifically substantiates the close connection between religious values and civil society, the role of religious values in strengthening human dignity, justice, tolerance, and interethnic harmony. As a result of the research, it is concluded that religious values are a philosophical foundation that ensures the spiritual stability of Uzbek society and strengthens social harmony.

Entrance

Since the years of independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the approach to religious values has fundamentally changed. If during the totalitarian regime religious beliefs and values were discriminated against, religious freedom was limited, today they are recognized as an important spiritual factor of national development.

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, said: "No nation can live apart from its history, its religion." In the modern era of New Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has formulated a new religious policy based on the principle of "Freedom of conscience and religious tolerance." The goal of this policy is to ensure the harmonious development of secularism and civil society while preserving religious values. Religious values are an important spiritual force that shapes humanity's spiritual life, moral views, faith, and stabilizes society. After Uzbekistan gained independence, important legal, spiritual, and organizational work was carried out to restore religious values and ensure religious freedom.

Including:

In 1992, the principle of "Freedom of conscience" was enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 31)

In 1998, the Law "On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations" was adopted.

Religious educational institutions, in particular, scientific centers named after Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, and Imam Moturidi, have been established

The study of religious heritage and its transmission to the younger generation has been elevated to the level of state policy.

These changes serve to restore the role of religious values in public life, to separate religion from politics, and to make it the main factor of spiritual life.

At the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, fundamental reforms are being implemented in the religious and educational sphere. The "New Uzbekistan Strategy" defines the preservation of religious values and the strengthening of religious tolerance and interfaith harmony as one of the priority areas. In the construction of civil society, religious values shape a person's inner culture and moral responsibility. Religious values are the spiritual foundation of social order, honesty, justice, peace, and tolerance.

In the global information age, a new, scientific-philosophical approach to religious values is necessary. Because religious values should be studied not only within the framework of worship or rituals, but also as a cultural, educational, and philosophical system of social consciousness.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, attention to religious values is an important spiritual direction of state policy. During the years of independence, freedom of religion and belief was ensured, and a policy of respect for religious and spiritual heritage was formed.

In the conditions of New Uzbekistan, religious values have become the foundation of human dignity, spiritual awakening, interethnic harmony, and social stability. They are of great importance in strengthening spiritual immunity in society and educating the younger generation in the spirit of national pride and patriotism.

Thus, a deep study of religious values and their harmonization with the concept of modern development is a philosophical and strategic necessity for the future development of Uzbekistan.

Religious values are one of the main spiritual factors ensuring the spiritual balance of a person's beliefs, moral views, and society. From a philosophical point of view, religion shapes a person's perception of the world, the way of understanding being, as well as moral criteria. Therefore, religious values are valued as the spiritual foundation of society.

In the history of Uzbekistan, Islam has played an active role not only as a religious system, but also as a source of cultural and spiritual awakening. In the works of such scholars as Alisher Navoi, Bahauddin Naqshband, Ahmad Yassavi, religious values are combined with the ideas of humanism, justice, and kindness.

During the period of New Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms were carried out in the religious and spiritual sphere. In particular, the establishment of such institutions as the Imam Bukhari International Research Center, the Center of Islamic Civilization, and the Imam Termizi Center allows for the scientific study of religious heritage and its correct transmission to the minds of young people.

The sustainable development of society depends, first of all, on the inner worldview of a person. Religious values, on the other hand, educate a person in the spirit of moral purity, honesty, tolerance, and patience. Therefore, the restoration of religious values is an integral part of the process of spiritual renewal.

From a philosophical point of view, religious values form the mechanism of spiritual integration in society - that is, they unite representatives of different nationalities, beliefs, and

cultures around common human values. In today's era of globalization, the strengthening of the principle of religious tolerance is of decisive importance in strengthening social harmony.

The role of religious values in educating the younger generation in the national spirit and as spiritually mature individuals is invaluable. The introduction of religious and educational subjects in Uzbekistan's education system, including courses such as "Religious Studies" and "Fundamentals of National Values," is a practical expression of attention in this direction. Religious values equip young people with moral immunity and protect them from extremist and radical ideas. In this sense, religious and educational education is one of the important directions of today's socio-philosophical development.

List of references:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2022.
2. Karimov I. A. Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2008.
3. "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi". – Toshkent: Adolat, 2022.
4. Vijdon erkinligi va diniy tashkilotlar to'g'risida"gi Qonun. – Toshkent, 1998.
5. Islom Karimov nomidagi Respublika Ma'naviyat va ma'rifat markazi materiallari, 2023.
6. Abdullayev A. Diniy qadriyatlarning ijtimoiy falsafasi. – Toshkent: Fan, 2019.
7. Yusupov R. Islom va milliy o'zlik. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2020.
8. Imom Moturidiy xalqaro ilmiy-tadqiqot markazi nashrlari. – Toshkent, 2024.

